

Case Study on the Current Status and Existing Issues of Japanese Language Courses for Minor Languages in Wenzhou City

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The article takes schools in Wenzhou that offer Japanese language courses for the college entrance examination as an example. Based on the analysis of the current situation of Japanese language teaching in Wenzhou's college entrance examination, the article uses a case study to analyze the existing problems in Wenzhou's Japanese language teaching for the college entrance examination. It proposes suggestions such as arranging Japanese class time reasonably, improving Japanese language teaching teacher resources, addressing students' own problems, improving teacher-student communication, guiding and encouraging students to learn independently, and enhancing students' confidence in learning.

Keywords: Wenzhou, College Entrance Examination Japanese, Problems and Challenges

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1. Introduction

Since the resumption of the college entrance examination in the 1970s, Japanese and Russian have been included in the foreign language system of the exam. Starting in 2003, the Ministry of Education explicitly stipulated that the foreign languages for the college entrance examination include English, Japanese, Russian, and others. In 2014, the State Council's "Implementation Opinions on Deepening the Reform of the Examination and Enrollment System" further clarified that the foreign languages for the college entrance examination encompass English, Japanese, Russian, German, French, Spanish, and others, reaffirming the importance of minor language education. In 2017, the "General High School Curriculum Plan (2017 Edition)" issued by the Ministry of Education specified that high school foreign languages include English, Japanese, Russian, German, French, and Spanish. To fully accommodate the actual conditions of minor languages—such as their relatively limited popularity compared to English and students' shorter exposure to these languages—the difficulty level of minor language exam papers should be 5 to 10 percentage points lower than that of English[1].

After entering the keyword "Gaokao Japanese" in China National Knowledge Infrastructure, 140 related studies were successfully retrieved. When entering the keyword "College Entrance Examination Japanese Zhejiang", it was found that only Wu Rongbin's "Advantages of College Entrance Examination Japanese over College Entrance Examination English"[2] was successfully retrieved. In other words, research on the Japanese language aspect of the college entrance examination has not yet become a focus of attention for experts and scholars in Zhejiang Province, and there are few related studies. With the introduction of policies related to minority languages by the government, the number of minority language candidates is increasing day by day. The number of Japanese language candidates in the 2019 college entrance examination reached about 48000, and the number of Japanese language candidates in Zhejiang Province also exceeded 6400[3], showing an increasing trend in recent years. Therefore, understanding the current situation and existing problems of offering Japanese courses in high school entrance exams in relevant regions of Zhejiang Province has certain practical significance.

2. Literature Review

Different experts and scholars have conducted research on the Japanese language proficiency of the college entrance examination in various regions of China from different perspectives. Firstly, from the perspective of various regions across the country, Wang Yingfang elaborated on the prospects of diversified cooperation and study abroad for Japanese language candidates in the Shanghai college entrance examination based on their strengths and weaknesses. Yin Zhicheng, based on the advantages and disadvantages of Japanese language in the college entrance examination, analyzed the current situation and development trend of Japanese language teaching in Hubei Province, and proposed strategies for the development of Japanese language in Hubei Province. Based on the background and policies of the Japanese language entrance examination in Hebei Province, Zhang Shaohua analyzed the current situation and problems of Japanese language entrance examination education in Hebei Province, and proposed measures from the aspects of textbooks, teacher resources, establishment of Japanese teaching mode, and implementation of Japanese practical application activities[4]. In addition, Qin Xiaocong, Zhang Jinlong, and others conducted a survey of Japanese language students taking the college entrance examination through questionnaires. By analyzing the survey results, they comprehensively analyzed the current situation of Japanese language teaching in the college entrance examination. Yao Xinyu analyzed the recent college entrance examination Japanese composition and proposed specific strategies[5]. The above scholars have analyzed the Japanese language teaching for the college entrance examination in different regions of China from different perspectives.

From the perspective of various regions in Zhejiang Province, Wu Rongbin found through investigation and analysis of the current situation of Japanese language in the Zhejiang college entrance examination that compared to English, the Chinese character system of Japanese language in the college entrance examination results in a smaller vocabulary memory, fewer question types, more objective questions, and a relatively simple difficulty for Chinese people. In addition, except for some majors that are particularly related to English, there

are not many restrictions for Japanese language students in the college entrance examination when filling out their application forms. There are also opportunities for studying abroad or entering Japanese language majors in universities for further education, and the future is promising[6]. Xu Hui et al. elaborated on the current situation of a surge in Japanese language students in the college entrance examination and the increasing demand for minority language talents in the country. They discovered the problem of a shortage of minority language talents in various parts of Zhejiang and proposed that the development of minority languages should be encouraged and supported, and more composite minority language talents should be cultivated[7]. Wang Zhaocheng and others analyzed the current development status of Japanese language students in the college entrance examination and found that the survival of Japanese language students is limited by the colleges and majors they apply for, the difficulty of English learning, and the fact that the designated talent training program for Japanese language majors is mostly applicable to "zero starting point" students, resulting in a waste of learning time. They proposed measures such as launching a three in one enrollment system for Japanese language majors and promoting the construction of courses such as "College Japanese" in universities to promote better connection between the college entrance examination Japanese language and universities[8]. Pan Cheng, Zhang Wenbi, and others took Hangzhou Dongfang Middle School as an example and conducted in-depth analysis from the advantages, disadvantages, opportunities, problems, and challenges of Japanese language teaching in the school through the AHP-SSWOT analysis method. Combined with the actual development strategy of the school, they put forward suggestions to promote the development of Japanese language education and students[9]. Taking Jiaying Foreign Language School as an example, Zhu Lina, Yan Yan, and others talked about the establishment process of the school's small language characteristic education from the logical starting point, action path, highlight retrospective, and future direction, and achieved success in teaching Japanese and other small languages, expressing hope for the future development of small language teaching. The above literature provides a certain literature foundation for the study of Japanese in the college entrance examination and has significant academic value.

However, from the above literature, it can be seen that there is currently little research in the academic community on the current situation, problems, and other aspects of the Japanese language proficiency in the Wenzhou college entrance examination. Based on literature research, this article visits schools and related educational institutions in Wenzhou that offer Japanese language courses for the college entrance examination to understand the current situation of Japanese language teaching, analyze existing problems, and propose corresponding suggestions for addressing the issues.

3. Research Subject

(1) Overview of Japanese Language Teaching in Wenzhou High School

In order to understand the current situation of Japanese language teaching in the Wenzhou college entrance examination, the research team visited several schools that offer Japanese language courses, including Wenzhou Private First Experimental School, Wenzhou Xiaoqiu Middle School, Wenzhou City University, Wenzhou Yingcai Middle School, and Eastern European Middle School. Wenzhou Private First Experimental School has been offering Japanese language courses for the college entrance examination since 2021, with 2 classes and around 40 students. Wenzhou Xiaoqiu Middle School has been offering the college entrance examination Japanese language program for many years. There are one to two classes with around 20 students each, and each class is accompanied by a Japanese teacher. Wenzhou City University has been offering Japanese courses for three years, and about 10% of the total students choose Japanese, with two Japanese teachers. Wenzhou Yingcai Middle School will implement the "Three Part Foreign Language" plan after 2022, officially including Japanese as a foreign language course option. Currently, more than 200 students have chosen Japanese as their foreign language for the college entrance examination. More than 50 students in Eastern European high schools take elective courses such as Japanese. Through investigation, it was found that many schools have been offering Japanese courses for three to four years, but most of the Japanese courses are taught through cooperation with external Japanese language institutions, and there are very few Japanese teachers in the schools themselves.

Next, taking Wenzhou Private First Experimental School as an example, analyze the current situation and existing problems of Japanese language in the Wenzhou college entrance examination. The reason for choosing Wenzhou Private First Experimental School is that it is an internship and practice base for students from the School of Foreign Languages at Wenzhou University. Every year, many undergraduate and graduate students from Wenzhou University intern at the school. At the same time, the school has close teaching and research cooperation with Wenzhou University, and they have a better understanding of each other.

(2) Overview of Wenzhou Private First Experimental School and Japanese Language Teaching

The research object of this study is Wenzhou Private First Experimental School. Wenzhou Private First Experimental School is a twelve year integrated private boarding school directly under the Wenzhou Education Bureau. It is located on the banks of the Oujiang River and beside the Furong Mountain, adjacent to the hometown of overseas Chinese and accompanied by the Flower City. The school was founded in August 2008, formerly known as Wenzhou Zhongyi Foreign Language School; In September 2013, it was renamed as Wenzhou Private First Experimental School; In May 2017, Lida Education Group officially signed a contract with Peking University New Century Education Group to carry out joint education. Wenzhou Private First Experimental School was renamed as Peking University New Century Wenzhou Affiliated School. The school currently covers an area of 150 acres, with a building area of 100000 square meters. It also has a 150 acre STEAM study farm, consisting of primary, junior high, and high school departments, with a total of 88 teaching classes, over 520 faculty members, and more than 2900 students. The school has 12 leading figures in various disciplines, including professor level teachers, provincial special grade teachers, and municipal famous teachers and homeroom teachers, including first prize winners of provincial high-quality courses, experts in middle and high school entrance examination proposition and examination, and hosts of provincial and municipal famous teacher studios. The overall strength of the teachers is high. In addition, the school also has a team of professional "overseas returnee" teachers (15 of whom have obtained degrees overseas and 37 have studied and trained abroad).

On the basis of practicing the educational philosophy of "comprehensive development and adaptability", the school takes the school motto of "independence, confidence, inclusiveness, and creativity" as the core of cultural construction, takes curriculum construction and reform as the starting point, and highlights the future characteristics of education and management as the foundation of sustainable development. The school combines technology and humanities to explore a seamless connection between primary and secondary education. At present, the school is one of the first batch of pilot schools for comprehensive reform of private education in China, one of the first 20 pilot window schools for comprehensive reform of private education in Wenzhou City, a standardized school for compulsory education in Zhejiang Province, a precision teaching experimental project school in Wenzhou City, the first batch of "Love Reading" project research community schools for primary and secondary schools in Wenzhou City, the second batch of STEAM education project pilot schools in Wenzhou City, and a selection base for the Cambridge Chuying project in Wenzhou. The series of measures taken by the school to establish itself based on quality have effectively enhanced its soft power, expanded its social reputation and cultural influence, and become a high-quality education brand widely trusted and recognized by parents in Wenzhou.

Since its establishment in 2008, Wenzhou Private First Experimental School has mainly focused on English language learning for its students until 2020. Starting from the second half of 2020, students and their parents began to call for the establishment of Japanese language courses in minority languages. The school leadership department attaches great importance to this and has specially organized a meeting on the topic of "Introducing Japanese Language Courses for Small Languages" to discuss the course situation. After discussion at the meeting, it was decided to offer Japanese language courses starting from 2021. At the same time, through public recruitment, we have specially hired one full-time Japanese language teacher. In addition, there are pre school trial classes and relevant briefing sessions on the Japanese language for the college entrance examination before the official start of classes, with the aim of enabling students and their parents to better understand the Japanese language curriculum for the college entrance examination.

Starting from the announcement of the launch of Japanese language courses in 2021, approximately 25 students out of over 200 students from 6 classes have registered for the trial classes of the Japanese language courses (a total of 8 trial classes). 19 students from the 2021 class have officially started learning Japanese. The other 6 individuals have decided to continue learning English due to reasons such as not liking Japanese and finding it difficult to learn. From the course schedule, there are a total of five classes scheduled from Monday to Friday, plus two classes on Saturday, making a total of seven classes per week. Due to the fact that students who choose courses come from various classes within the same period, there are certain restrictions on class time. Except for the two classes on Saturdays, all other courses are taught in the evening, which also has a certain impact on teaching. The students of the 2022 grade have also officially started learning Japanese language courses. A total of 27 students have registered to study in this session. Therefore, there is one teacher for the Japanese language course in the entire school's college entrance examination, two classes, and a total of 46 students. Due to the restructuring of the school structure, the Japanese teacher who was originally registered in 2023 resigned, and the school began to cooperate with external teaching institutions for education. Therefore, the teachers currently serving as Japanese language teachers are dispatched to the school by cooperative external organizations to carry out teaching.

4. Existing Problems

After in-depth research by the research team, it was found that currently, Wenzhou Private First Experimental School has problems in Japanese language teaching, such as a shortage of teaching staff, heavy teaching tasks for teachers, unreasonable teaching time arrangements, improper student management systems, and the need to improve students' attitudes towards learning Japanese.

Firstly, challenges in Japanese language teaching. Firstly, there are issues within the students themselves. According to the author's research, most students who choose to study Japanese courses do so because their English grades are relatively poor and they want to improve their scores in the college entrance examination by learning Japanese.

Generally speaking, learning any language requires persistent effort, such as mastering vocabulary, understanding grammar, conducting daily exercises, and cooperating with previewing and reviewing. These are necessary conditions for laying the foundation of the language. Students who give up on learning English and Japanese may have certain problems in their learning methods and attitudes. After transferring to Japanese, this group of students still have attitudes and practices similar to those when learning English. Therefore, some students have many problems in the process of learning Japanese, such as low efficiency in listening to lectures, failure to follow the learning cycle of previewing and reviewing, insufficient vocabulary mastery, and weak grammar knowledge. At the same time, some students still have a certain degree of laziness and exhibit phenomena such as improper and positive learning attitudes. Secondly, schools do not place enough emphasis on Japanese language teaching. As of now, the relevant departments of the school lack a set of plans and guidelines for Japanese language teaching. The teaching of minority languages in schools lacks specialization and specialization, and there is limited communication and cooperation with universities, as well as a lack of guidance from university experts. Meanwhile, apart from Japanese language teachers, no one has inquired about the current situation and existing problems of Japanese language teaching.

Secondly, the course schedule is unreasonable. Due to the synchronization of English classes and Japanese classes, and the fact that English classes are mostly scheduled in the afternoon or evening, Japanese classes can only be scheduled in the afternoon or evening. When other students are learning English in the classroom, students learning Japanese can only leave the classroom. After students leave the class, the school lacks a unified Japanese after-school learning management mechanism, resulting in students being unsupervised. This not only makes students waste their time and studies, but also makes it difficult to ensure the continuity and effectiveness of their Japanese language learning, ultimately affecting their academic performance. And language courses require memorizing and memorizing a large number of knowledge points, but since Japanese classes are usually scheduled in the afternoon or evening, students are prone to physiological and cognitive fatigue due to continuous learning.

This state directly restricts students' focus and knowledge absorption rate, thereby affecting the final learning effectiveness and quality.

Thirdly, there is a shortage of teaching staff and heavy teaching tasks. As mentioned above, the school currently offers two Japanese classes with only one teacher. For example, Japanese language teachers have 18 classes per week, which is 6 more classes than English teachers. In addition, as high school students have already entered the second year of high school, they not only need to teach the basic courses in textbooks well, but also need to strengthen extracurricular exercises on weekdays. In this way, in addition to regular classes on weekdays, teachers also have to tutor and grade a large amount of extracurricular homework, resulting in heavy teaching tasks. Apart from class time, there is not enough time to guide students' learning after class.

5. Related Suggestions

Regarding the above issues, the following suggestions are suggested:

Firstly, we need to address the challenges in Japanese language teaching. Firstly, in response to students' own problems, it is necessary to establish effective communication between teachers and students, guide and encourage students to learn independently, and enhance their confidence in learning. On the one hand, we need to strengthen the construction of academic atmosphere, for example, by arranging full-time teachers to supervise students' learning and create a good learning atmosphere. On the other hand, we need to break the traditional teaching mode and implement a diversified classroom teaching mode that combines theory and practice. For example, we can increase interactive activities in Japanese classes to cultivate students' language communication skills; By translating and appreciating Japanese anime and drama works, we aim to stimulate students' interest and enthusiasm for learning Japanese. At the same time, we will improve the school's study abroad system, targeting students who cannot enter their ideal universities after the college entrance examination and achieving their dream of attending university through studying abroad.

It is suggested that the school strengthen communication and cooperation with relevant educational institutions in Japan, and provide a platform for students who need to study abroad to further their education and study abroad. Secondly, at the school level, emphasis should be placed on Japanese language education. We can strengthen cooperation with universities, such as Wenzhou Medical University, Wenzhou University, etc., all of which have Japanese language majors and some experience in Japanese language curriculum construction, teacher training, etc. Through cooperation, we can specify more detailed Japanese language teaching policies and promote the development of Japanese language teaching. We can learn from the distinctive Japanese language education path of other schools, for example, we can draw on the distinctive education path and philosophy of Jiaxing Foreign Language School to promote the diversified and distinctive development of minority languages. Attaching importance to the cultivation of small language talents can increase the investment in Japanese education resources. For example, by relying on the Internet to integrate more high-quality resources, or improve the hardware facilities of small language Japanese, arrange special Japanese self-study classrooms for students learning Japanese and other measures, promote the development of Japanese teaching in schools by providing resources and technical support for Japanese teaching. Efforts should be made to pay attention to the enrollment rate, Japanese scores, and teaching situation of Japanese language candidates. Tian Yan once proposed measures to strengthen the construction of academic atmosphere, establish a sound management system, including reviewing teachers' teaching qualifications and students' course selection qualifications. It is necessary to equip a complete teaching supervision system suitable for public elective courses, conduct teaching evaluations in a timely manner, point out existing problems, provide guidance in a timely manner, clarify teaching objectives, and improve teaching quality[10] and other measures to avoid misunderstandings among parents of candidates about learning Japanese and enhance the persuasiveness of Japanese language teaching.

Secondly, arrange Japanese class time reasonably. The school should coordinate with Japanese language teachers to arrange class schedules.

To unify foreign language teaching time, for example, while other students are studying English, Japanese language teachers can organize students who are learning Japanese to study or study together, or assign homework to students to make full use of this time to learn Japanese. In this way, it can not only avoid wasting time, but also enable students to study seriously. At the same time, it is hoped that schools will attach importance to Japanese language teaching and plan lesson schedules reasonably, such as arranging early Japanese reading to improve the memory of foreign language knowledge points; Unify the class schedule for English and Japanese, arrange the order of classes reasonably, and avoid teaching fatigue and learning fatigue caused by continuous classes.

Thirdly, improve the teaching staff of Japanese language. Schools should improve the teaching staff and level of minority languages by hiring experts and scholars from various universities, hiring external teachers through school enterprise cooperation, and introducing outstanding Japanese language talents from home and abroad. For example, schools can collaborate with universities that offer Japanese language majors to hire specialized Japanese language teachers, thereby enhancing their teaching staff; Alternatively, schools can collaborate with external Japanese language training institutions. Some already mature educational institutions have extensive experience in Japanese language teaching, which can improve the quality of Japanese language teaching in schools. At the same time, dividing teaching tasks, clarifying and refining teaching tasks, and alleviating the full-time pressure on individual Japanese teachers. A class can be arranged to be led by one or more Japanese language teachers, allowing the teachers to have more energy to manage the Japanese class and pay attention to students' learning situation, thereby improving the quality of teaching.

6. Conclusion

This article takes a school in Wenzhou that offers Japanese language courses for the college entrance examination as a case study, and based on research, understands the pre transfer and existing problems of Japanese language courses for the Wenzhou college entrance examination.

The development of Japanese language in the college entrance examination has been rapid due to its advantages such as easy entry, fast score improvement, and short learning cycle, but at the same time, it has also exposed many problems. Schools should constantly adjust and view current grades and issues correctly. Strengthen the teaching staff of Japanese language education, improve the Japanese language teaching system, strengthen student management, continuously accumulate experience, enhance students' interest in learning, improve their academic performance, provide more opportunities for Japanese language candidates to further their studies and employment, and bring more blessings to candidates. As it is a case study, although the conclusions of this article to some extent illustrate some issues, they cannot represent the overall situation of Japanese language teaching in the college entrance examination in Wenzhou city. In the following research, the number of research subjects will be increased, and the scope of investigation will be further expanded to sort out and analyze the Japanese language situation in the Wenzhou college entrance examination from a macro perspective.

References

- [1] Xu Hui et al. (2021). Research on the current situation and problems of small language teaching in Zhejiang Universities. *Wenzhou Journal*, 4.
- [2] Wu Rongbin. (2017). The advantages of comparing Japanese to english in the college entrance examination. *Exam Weekly*, 32.
- [3] Wang Yingfang. (2012). Analysis of the current situation and prospects of small language (Japanese) candidates in the college entrance examination. *Exam Weekly*, 52.
- [4] Yin Zhicheng. (2018). Analysis of the current situation of Japanese language education in Hubei province's college entrance examination. *Chinese and Foreign Entrepreneurs*, 14.
- [5] Zhang Shaohua. (2022 January). Analysis of the current situation of Japanese language entrance examination education in Hebei province. *Journal of Hengshui University*.
- [6] Yao Xinyu. (2024). Analysis of college entrance examination Japanese composition teaching based on the differences in theme categories between college entrance examination Japanese and EJU composition. *Jiaying Literature*, 20.

[7] Wang Zhaocheng, Ye Yaorong, Sheng Xuewu, & Xie Pei. (2019). A brief discussion on the adaptation issues and solutions for Japanese language students in the college entrance examination. *Gaokao*, 06.

[8] Pan Cheng, & Zhang Wenbi. (2020). A discussion on contemporary Chinese middle school Japanese education based on AHP-SSWOT analysis - Taking Hangzhou Dongfang middle school as an example. *Japanese Education and Japanese Studies Research*, 00.

[9] Juliana, & Yan Yan. (2024). The ten year road of specialized education for small languages in ordinary high schools - The practice of Jiaying foreign language school. *Middle School Edition (Teaching Management)*, 11.

[10] Xu Hui, Sun Yunsun, & Zhang Zhicheng. (2021). One hundred years of overseas Chinese in Li'ao. *Jilin University Press*, pp. 95-98.

[11] An Rong, Jiang Yifan, & Hui Chaoyue. (2021). *Analysis of the current situation and problems of Japanese language in the college entrance examination*, 10.

[12] Juliana, & Yan Yan. (2024). The ten year road of specialized education for small languages in ordinary high schools - The practice of Jiaying foreign language school. *Middle School Edition (Teaching Management)*, 11.

[13] Tian Yan. (2009). Difficulties and solutions in the construction of minority language courses in universities. *China Electric Power Education*, 01.

Footnotes

[1] Xu Hui et al., "Research on the Status and Issues of Minor Language Teaching in Zhejiang Universities," **Wenzhou Journal**, No. 4, 2021, p. 44.

[2] Wu Rongbin: "Advantages of College Entrance Examination Japanese over College Entrance Examination English", *Exam Weekly*, Issue 32, 2017.

[3] Xu Hui et al.: "Research on the Current Situation and Problems of Small Language Teaching in Zhejiang Universities", *Wenzhou Journal*, Issue 4, 2021, pp. 44-45.

[4] Zhang Shaohua: "Analysis of the Current Situation of Japanese Language Entrance Examination Education in Hebei Province" *Journal of Hengshui University*, January 2022.

[5] Yao Xinyu: "Teaching Analysis of College Entrance Examination Japanese Composition Based on the Differences in Theme Categories between College Entrance Examination Japanese and EJU Composition", *Jiaying Literature*, 2024 Issue 20.

[6] Wu Rongbin: "The advantages of Japanese language in the college entrance examination compared to English in the high school entrance examination", *Exam Weekly*, Issue 32, 2017.

[7] Xu Hui: "Research on the Current Situation and Problems of Minority Language Teaching in Zhejiang Universities", *Wenzhou Journal*, Issue 04, 2021.

[8] Wang Zhaocheng, Ye Yaorong, Sheng Xuewu, Xie Pei: "A Brief Discussion on the Problems and Solutions of Adapting to Japanese Language Source Universities in the College Entrance Examination", *Gaokao*, 2019, Issue 06.

[9] Pan Cheng, Zhang Wenbi: "A Discussion on Contemporary Chinese Middle School Japanese Language Education Based on AHP-SSWOT Analysis - Taking Hangzhou Dongfang Middle School as an Example", *Japanese Language Education and Japanese Studies Research*, 2020, Issue 00.

[10] Tian Yan: "Difficulties and Solutions in the Construction of Small Language Courses in Colleges and Universities", *"China Electric Power Education"*, Issue 01, 2009.

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